

June 30, 2019

Effect of Mancomax on Germination and Fungi Associated of Sesame Seeds in Côte d'Ivoire

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Abstract

Sesame is an oilseed crop that is growing in many developing countries for its good market value and new economic opportunities. However, its cultivation is however compromised by parasitic constraints which strongly reduce yields. This study was carried out on fungal strains associated with seeds and the effectiveness of a fungicide Mancomax. The detection of fungal strains associated with sesame was made using the blotting paper method. The efficiency of Mancomax 80 WP (Mancozeb) was evaluated on the seeds of four sesame accessions in order to evaluate its effectiveness in inhibiting the growth and development of seed-borne fungi.

*The contamination rate of the sesame varieties studied varies according to the accessions with a diversity of associated fungal strains. These fungi; especially *Curvularia sp*, *Aspergillus sp*, and *Fusarium sp* are fungi that produce mycotoxin that inhibits seed germination. The results show that this fungicide inhibits fungal infection to 100% for all concentrations studied for Mancomax effects on seed disinfection. Mancomax may be an ideal disinfectant to reduce the low germination rate of sesame seeds.*

Keywords: *sesame, Mancozeb, Mancomax, inhibition, fungicide*

1. INTRODUCTION

Sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) is one of the most important oil-seed crops in the world. It has great economic potential because of its high oil and protein content (Sadou *α* Amoukou 2002, Sene *et al.*, 2018). Sesame oil is used as edible oil, in paints and soap industry and also has great medicinal value (Anonym 2016, Okandza *α al.*, 2017). Asia provides 70% of world production while Africa's share is 15%. Demand in the international sesame market is growing. Sesame presents itself as a culture capable of providing substantial income in sub-Saharan Africa. In Sénégal, for example, sesame generates more than 700 million FCFA per crop (Diouf, 2002). In Burkina Faso, sesame is the second agricultural export product from 2002 with more than 5 billion annual revenues (Traoré, 2012).

In Côte d'Ivoire, sesame cultivation is relatively new. Indeed, sesame was a plant associated with the main crops (cotton, yam, etc.) for the occasional needs of agricultural populations. Today, sesame cultivation is practiced in the North mainly in Touba. However, yields remain low because of many abiotic and biotic factors. Knowledge of production systems, pests, diseases, and seed quality can help boost the growth of this crop in Côte d'Ivoire. Quality seeds are the guarantee of vigorous plants in culture. However, the seeds currently used come from all walks of life without any guarantee of quality. As well, no systematic work has been carried out on the seed borne fungi of sesame in Côte d'Ivoire. This situation led the Biotechnology and Improvement Laboratory of the University Jean Lorougnon Guédé (Côte d'Ivoire) to evaluate the sanitary quality of the seeds used by the producers. More specifically, it aims to study fungal strains associated with seeds and to test the efficacy of a fungicide commonly used and available on the local market.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. Plant material

Ten sesame accessions collected from nine localities of Touba (650 km from Abidjan) were used for the study. They are distributed according to color, provenance and their name in the local language (Table 1).

Table 1 : Sesame accessions used

Accession code	Color	Localities	Local Name
SBBGL	White	Lalosso	Benaigbê
SBBGTo	White	Tokro	Benaigbê
SRYD	Red	Dioman	Yeya
SBBGD 1	White	Dioman	Benaigbê
SBBGD 2	White	Dioman	Benaigbê
SBBGS	White	Salla	Benaigbê
SBBGF	White	Fouenan	Benaigbê
SBBGFI	White	Fouala	Benaigbê
SBBGY	White	Yalla	Benaigbê
SBBGYe	White	Yekro	benaigbê
SBBGT	White	Tienko	benaigbê
SNBFD	Black	Dioman	benaifi

2.2. Pesticide

Mancomax 80WP (Mancozeb) Fungicide was used for seeds treatment to evaluate its effectiveness in inhibiting the growth and development of seed-borne sesame fungi. Mancozeb is Dithiocarbamate fungicide. It has been chosen for its accessibility by the local producers and its massive use by them.

2.3. Methods

The detection of fungal strains of sesame was made by the blotting paper method. Twelve Petri dishes containing moistened blotting paper were used per variety. seeds were placed in each Petri dishes. Seeds were sterilized with 0.3% sodium hypo chloride solution for 3 minutes and Twenty five selected seeds were placed in five each Petri plates. The Petri dishes with seeds were then incubated in the dark and moistened at room temperature for seven days in the laboratory condition. Fungi associated with the seeds were recorded and examined from 3 days after incubation. Fungi were counted and described according to color and texture and identified according to Barnett and Hunter (1972). The identification is based on the mode of conidiogenesis and the characteristics of the mycelium.

2.4. Effects of Mancomax for fungi disinfection on sesame seeds

The SNBFD, SRYD, SBBGT and SBBGL accessions were used to perform this test. The SNBFD and SRYD accessions were chosen because they recorded the highest number of fungal colonies. SBBGT and SBBGL because they had the highest germination rates. Efficacy of Mancomax was evaluated at, 5 g / l (the manufacturer's dose). Five Petri dishes were used for each accession with 3 repetitions. The Petri dishes were incubated in the dark under laboratory conditions (27 ± 2 ° C) for 7 days. The presence or absence of fungal colonies and the germination percentage was calculated by using the following formula:

$$\text{Germination (\%)} = \frac{\text{Number of seeds germinated}}{\text{Total number of seeds planted}} \times 100$$

2.5. The effective dose for fungal disinfection and optimum germinal quality

This test is the continuation of the previous one; it is a question of determining the optimal dose which combines the effectiveness of fungicidal action and high level of germination. The SNBFD, SRYD, SBBGT and SBBGL accessions were used. Fungicide (Mancomax) solution was prepared at different concentrations: D1 (5g / l, manufacturer's dose), D2 (2.5g / l), D3 (1.125g / l) and D4 (0.625g / l). The sesame seeds were soaked in mancomax solutions for 10 min and in sterile distilled water for the controls. Twenty five Seeds were placed on blotting paper moistened in Petri dishes. The following treatments were obtained: T1: seeds and substrates dipped in the different doses of Mancomax; T2: seeds soaked in fungicide doses and substrates soaked in sterile distilled water T3: seeds dipped in distilled water and substrates soaked in fungicide doses. Five Petri dishes were used for each treatment per accession. Three replicates for each of the treatment including control was maintained. The Petri dishes were incubated in the dark under

Aspergillus flavus

Aspergillus niger

Rhizomucor sp

Drachslera poae

Fusarium oxysporum

Fusarium sp.

Lasiodiplodia theobromae

Curvularia lunata

Alternaria sesami

Alternaria alternata

Non identifié

Fig. 2: Morphological characteristic fungi isolated

Table 2: Fungi identified by accessions

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Accession de sésame	Champignon isolé
SBBGL	<i>Curvularia lunata</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Fusarium sp</i>
SBBGT _o	<i>Curvularia lunata</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Fusarium sp</i>
SRYD	<i>Curvularia lunata</i> , <i>Alternaria alternata</i> , <i>Lasiodiplodia theobromae</i> , <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> , <i>Fusarium sp</i> , <i>Drachslera poae</i> , Ascomycète (non identifié)
SBBGD 1	<i>Curvularia lunata</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Fusarium sp</i>
SBBGD 2	<i>Curvularia lunata</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Fusarium sp</i>
SBBGS	<i>Curvularia lunata</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Fusarium sp</i>
SBBGF	<i>Curvularia lunata</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Fusarium sp</i>
SBBGFI	<i>Curvularia lunata</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Fusarium sp</i> , <i>Alternaria sesami</i>
SBBGY _e	<i>Curvularia lunata</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Fusarium sp</i>
SBBGT	<i>Curvularia lunata</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Fusarium sp</i>
SNBFD	<i>Curvularia lunata</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Rhizomucor sp.</i>

3.2. Efficacy of Mancomax for disinfection of sesame seeds

The application of Mancomax at the manufacturer's dose of 5 g / l 100% inhibited the growth of fungal strains on germinated sesame seeds. On the other hand, none of the varieties tested germinated. The manufacturer's dose inhibited 100% seed germination (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: Seed of sesame germination on blotting paper. A: untreated seed with seedlings and browned leaves; B: Ungerminated seeds treated with Mancomax (5 g / l)

3.3. Effective dose allowing seeds disinfection and an optimal germination quality.

The study of the effect of Mancomax disinfection on fungi colonization of sesame has shown that all the concentrations studied are effective with complete inhibition of fungal colonies. Unlike the germination rate which varied according to the varieties and concentrations of Mancomax. Determination of the effective Mancomax dose for fungi disinfection while maintaining an acceptable germination rate demonstrated that the germination rate was dependent on several interlocking factors. First, the germination rate depended on the accession. Indeed, the statistical analysis showed a variation of the germination rate from one accession to another. The SBBGT (V1), SBBGL (V2) and SRYD (V3) accessions are in the same homogeneity group, they statistically have the same germination rate (53-59%). Black sesame (SNBFD or V4) has the lowest germination rate. It is estimated at around 33% (Fig. 4). Also, the germination rate of the four accessions tested varied greatly depending on the treatments performed. Indeed, when tempering for 10 min the sesame seeds in Mancomax (T1) before sowing on blotter soaked in the same fungicide, the germination rate is considerably low compared to soaked seeds whose substrate (blotter) was not soaked (T2). The germination rate is 32% for T1 treatment against around 77% for T2 treatment. On the other hand, the germination rate of the T3 treatment (seeds not soaked on the hardened substrate) is statistically similar to that of T1 (Fig. 5). In addition, germination of sesame seeds was strongly influenced by the dose variation of Mancomax (Fig. 6). In fact, when the seed is treated at a dose of 5 g / l (D1 = manufacturer's dose), the germination rate of sesame seeds drops considerably (22%) compared to the D0 dose (98.61%). However, the reduction in Mancomax concentration leads to an increase in the germination rate. Thus, at the dose D2 (2.5 g / l) and D3 (1.25 g / l), the germination percentages are respectively 26.3 and 34.9% against 98.61% at the dose C (water treatment simple). The highest germination rate which is 70.19% against 98.61% for the control was

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obtained with the dose D4 (0.625 g / l). Statistical analysis also revealed a strong (highly significant) interaction between variety-treatment, variety-dose, treatment-dose and variety-treatment-dose. This implies that the combined action of the three factors leads to an even greater reduction in the germination rate.

Fig. 4: Effect of fungicide on the germination rate of sesame accessions

Fig. 5: Effect of fungicide treatment on sesame seeds germination

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Fig. 6: Effect various concentrations of Mancomax on seeds germination

4. DISCUSSION

This study shows that the contamination rate of the sesame varieties studied varies according to the accessions. The accession SBBGL has not recorded fungi development. The accessions SBBGD1, SBBGD2, SBBGY, SBBGD, SBBGF, SBBGT, and SBBGFL were very poorly colonized (1 to 4%) so that SNBFD (53%) and SRYD (16%) recorded the lowest rates of infection. higher. The SBBGD1, SBBGD2, SBBGY, SBBGS, SBBGF, SBBGT and SBBGFL accessions were very sparsely colonized (1-4%), while SNBFD (53%) and SRYD (16%) recorded the highest rates of infection. In general, white accessions exhibited low contamination rates unlike black SNBFD (53%) and SRYD red (16%) accessions. These results show that red and black varieties are more susceptible to infection than white varieties. This could explain the abundance of white varieties in the Ivorian markets compared to others. In addition, the agronomic performance of white varieties has been observed in different studies (Badiel *α al.*, 2016). According to Traore (2002), the white variety S42, instigated by research programs in Burkina Faso, is valued for the agronomic performance, resistance to external factors and for its color, hence its predominance in trade.

Seven fungi genera were identified: *Curvularia* sp., *Aspergillus* sp., *Alternaria* sp. *Lasiodiplodia* sp., *Fusarium* sp, *Drachslera* sp. and an unidentified Ascomycete. The presence of these fungi on sesame could be explained by the conditions of conservation of seeds. Indeed, during storage, seeds are subject to many parasitic attacks, including that of fungi. These fungi can cause deterioration in seed quality during storage, making it difficult to sell these products. They can also reduce the germination of these seeds. According to Yonoussa (2011), fungi in warehouses, especially *Fusarium* sp. can cause enormous damage including the decrease in germination power. In addition, Abdus and Ansar (1992), show that fungi diversity are associated with sesame in Pakistan, including *Alternaria sesami*, *Fusarium* sp., *Aspergillus* sp. and *Drechslera*.

C. lunata, *Fusarium* sp, and *A. niger* were found almost in all the accessions studied. Presence of *Curvularia* sp; *Apergillus* sp and *Fusarium* sp could negatively impact seeds germination. According to the Codex Alimentarius, *Curvularia* sp; *Apergillus* sp and *Fusarium* sp are fungi that produce mycotoxins thus could prevent seed germination (FAO, OMS, 2014). The pathogenicity of *Alternaria* sp. has been demonstrated by many studies in Pakistan (Naik *α al.*, 2014) and Korea (Young *α al.*, 2014). Also, the work of Shabnum, (2004) in Pakistan showed a diversity of fungi on seeds including cowpea. The author has shown that *Curvularia* sp., *Aspergillus* sp., *Alternaria* sp. *Fusarium* sp, *Drachslera* sp. *Penicillium* sp. and

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Cephalosporium sp. are able to infect seeds and decrease their germination. It also showed that *Aspergillus* sp. is dominant on all cultivars studied. These results are consistent with our work showing that *Aspergillus niger* is present on all accessions except SRYD.

Concerning the effect of Mancomax on seed disinfection, the results show that this fungicide inhibits fungal infection to 100% at all concentrations studied. Mancomax can completely inhibit fungal infections. Indeed, mancozeb, the active ingredient of Mancomax is a multisite fungicide, which allows it to act on several essential functions of pathogens hence its effectiveness. As for the germination of sesame seeds, the dose of 5 g / l gave 100% inhibition. For the other concentrations, the germination rates vary according to the varieties, the doses, and the treatments. SBBGT (V1), SBBGL (V2) and SRYD (V3) accessions had the highest germination rates (53-59%), while black sesame (SNBFD or V4) had the lowest germination rate (33%). These results could be explained by the strength of the accessions of sesame studied and/or their genotype. Seed storage conditions could also justify this low germination rate for SNBFD because the seeds had to be infected by the fungi during storage and thus reduced their germination.

The different concentrations of Mancomax significantly reduced germination rates which varied from 26.3 to 34.9% and 70.19% respectively at doses D2 (2.5g / l) and D3 (1.25g / l), D4 (0.625g / l). l) against 98.61% for the control dose. These results show that Macomax, whose active ingredient is Mancozeb, inhibits the germination of sesame seeds. Inhibition of wheat seed germination by a fungicide (Tebuconazole) has been observed by Amgoud (2015). This author showed that the germination rate of wheat seeds treated with Tebuconazole was reduced by 26.67% compared to the control. Also, the results show that the best germination rates are obtained when the seeds are soaked in Mancomax and they are grown on moistened blotting paper. Germination is poorer when the seed and substrate are soaked or when only the substrate is soaked in the fungicide. These results show that the intrinsic and exogenous factors at the seed strongly influence germination. In this study, it could be the genes (germination varies according to the varieties), the influence of the fungi and the toxicity of the pesticides. The fungi isolated in our study are pathogenic and subservient to the seed. Indeed, many studies have shown the pathogenicity of these fungi, especially *Curvularia* p., *Alternaria sesami*, *Alternaria alternata*, *Pestalotiopsis* sp, *Fusarium Oxysporum* et *Lasiodiplodia theobromae* (Djeugap, 2013).

5. CONCLUSION

This study shows that many fungi contaminate sesame varieties in Côte d'Ivoire. But the importance of contamination depended on accessions. In addition, the most contaminated accessions germinate less well. The less affected white accessions sprout better than the red (SRYD) and black (SNBFD) accessions. The identified fungi of these seeds are *Curvularia lunata*., *Aspergillus niger*, *Rhizomucor* sp., *Aspergillus flavus*, *Alternaria sesami*, *Alternaria alternate*, *Lasiodiplodia theobromae*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Fusarium* sp. and *Drachslera poae*. Among them, strains of *Curvularia* sp., *Alternaria* sp., *Fusarium* sp are known to be sesame pathogens in culture. In addition, Mancomax can effectively treat these fungi. However, to reduce its toxic effect on germination, it is necessary to reduce to 1 / 8th the dose recommended by the manufacturer.

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